

Sonifying Energy Consumption Using SpecSinGAN

Sandra Pauletto¹Adrián Barahona-Ríos²Vincenzo Madaghiale¹Yann Seznec¹¹ KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden² Department of Computer Science, University of York, UK¹{pauletto, vmad, yannse}@kth.se, ²ajbr501@york.ac.uk

ABSTRACT

In this paper we present a system for the sonification of the electricity drawn by different household appliances. The system uses SpecSinGAN as the basis for the sound design, which is an unconditional generative architecture that takes a single one-shot sound effect (e.g., a fire crackle) and produces novel variations of it. SpecSinGAN is based on single-image generative adversarial networks that learn from the internal distribution of a single training example (in this case the spectrogram of the sound file) to generate novel variations of it, removing the need of a large dataset. In our system, we use a python script in a Raspberry PI to receive the data of the electricity drawn by an appliance via a Smart Plug. The data is then sent to a Pure Data patch via Open Sound Control. The electricity drawn is mapped to the sound of fire, which is generated in real-time using Pure Data by mixing different variations of four fire sounds - a fire crackle, a low end fire rumble, a mid level rumble, and hiss - which were synthesised offline by SpecSinGAN. The result is a dynamic fire sound that is never the same, and that grows in intensity depending on the electricity consumption. The density of the crackles and the level of the rumbles increase with the electricity consumption. We pilot tested the system in two households, and with different appliances. Results confirm that, from a technical standpoint, the sonification system responds as intended, and that it provides an intuitive auditory display of the energy consumed by different appliances. In particular, this sonification is useful in drawing attention to “invisible” energy consumption. Finally, we discuss these results and future work.

1. INTRODUCTION

Smart home automation systems, based on Internet of Things (IoT) technology, can facilitate energy efficiency by providing users with data and information about their energy consumption, however research shows that these benefits can be undermined by the way information is presented to users [1, 2]. To address this issue, researchers are developing alternative ways to present energy information. Instead of borrowing from technologies and displays often associated with workplaces [3], novel designs focus on different

values such as playfulness and wonder [3], simplicity [4], and empathy for the space [5].

In this paper we present an alternative way to display per-appliance energy consumption that uses a sonification based on an everyday sound: the sound of fire. The immediate advantage of using fire as way to display energy is that the link between energy consumption and fire intensity is highly intuitive. The design exploits our common understanding of everyday sounds to make energy information and comparisons between appliances highly transparent and intuitive. This display can be understood by adults as well as children most probably anywhere in the world. This is possible because we are able to synthesise a continuous everyday sound, in this case fire, that is dynamic, plausible, and at the same time controllable. To do this we combine the use of SpecSinGAN [6], an unconditional generative architecture that is trained on a single sound effect and synthesises plausible novel variations of it, with sound design techniques from media production [7] - layering, sequencing and crossfading between different basic sonic elements to create a complex sound - in the Pure Data real-time software environment.

While a number of different continuous sounds can be synthesised using other techniques such as physical modelling, this approach widens the spectrum of possibilities as SpecSinGAN can use any sound sample as the source for synthesised variations. As a result, this technique becomes a very important sound design tool for creating sonifications based on everyday sounds, which have the potential to be more easily accepted and understood in displays for everyday use.

2. BACKGROUND

Occupant behaviour is commonly identified as one of the main causes of Energy Performance Gap (EPG), the difference between consumption of a building that have been predicted by a simulation and the actual measured ones [8, 9]. Research on effective energy consumption feedback, which ranges from visual displays [10, 11] to digital games based on real-time data [12], is trying to tackle this issue. A common way of providing feedback about energy consumption is through smart meters and smart plugs. Potential energy savings due to the deployment of smart meters have been estimated to 5-15% [13, 14]. These figures, however, depend on feedback delivery and context. Research shows that users engage with this kind of technology in the short term, however long-term engagement and behavioural effects are less clear [15]. Strengers [16]

argues that the reasons for the limitations might be found in the way feedback is designed which often overlooks how people behave at home. Human-Computer Interaction research attempts to tackle the shortcomings of conventional visual displays of energy consumption. Some contributions include affordance-based persuasion [17], gamification [18], as well as alternative visualisation techniques such as the Power-Aware Cord [19], the Energy-Aware Clock [20], lamps that change their color based on energy consumption [21].

More recently sound has emerged as a new, potentially more intuitive way to display energy consumption. Examples include the use of sonification to display complex electrical power systems [22], frequencies and voltage variations in a power grid [23], shower water consumption [24], or electric power consumption in a kitchen [25]. Using sound as a display of household data, often implies the introduction of new sounds in the everyday life of the occupants. If the sounds are not carefully designed, this might become a barrier for acceptance and engagement. Some research efforts in this area aim to address this issue by leveraging on our existing acceptance and understanding of everyday sounds in the household, as well as our cultural understanding of sound in media. For example, Foley sounds such as interactions between characters and objects, in films are used to portray subtle information about the story and characters [7, 26]). Research in this area include the development of workshop methods to better understand how users might relate everyday sounds and energy concepts [27], the creation of an energy efficient shower prototype that builds upon existing cultural associations between showering and singing [28], and the design of sonic implicit interactions to encourage energy saving behaviours [29]. The work presented in this paper contributes to this research effort. Since SpecSinGAN [6] allows us to synthesise plausible novel variations from a single sound effect, we can potentially use as a starting point for our sonification any everyday sound that we know our users are familiar with and happy to engage with.

The use of deep learning techniques (such as SpecSinGAN) to produce sound is commonly referred as neural audio synthesis [30]. Regarding the synthesis of sound effects using these techniques, there has been efforts to synthesise knocking sound effects [31], environmental sounds [32], footsteps [33] and explosion sounds [34] to name a few. Very recently, there have also been text-to-audio architectures that use natural language prompts to synthesise sounds [35–37]. Apart from SpecSinGAN, there are other approaches to synthesise audio training on reduced datasets, such as [38] that generates longer sequences from just 20 seconds of training data. Concerning non-deep learning and pure digital signal processing (DSP) approaches, in [39,40] they generate variations of percussive pre-recorded sounds. We use SpecSinGAN because 1) it allows us to train on any single one-shot sound effect that we can choose accordingly depending of the specifications of the project; 2) we do not need to rely on finding a large dataset of sounds that may be scarce; 3) SpecSinGAN generates short variations we can continuously trigger to produce an adap-

tive soundscape.

In the following sections we will describe the system, the pilot testing we conducted, and we will discuss the results of this testing as well as future work.

3. THE SYSTEM

3.1 SpecSinGAN

To source the sounds used by our sonification system we use SpecSinGAN [6], which is an unconditional generative architecture that is trained on a single sound effect and synthesises plausible novel variations of it. For this work, all sounds are synthesised offline and stored as audio files to be used in the sonification.

Generative adversarial networks (GANs) [41] are a deep learning modelling technique where (at least) two networks, the generator and the discriminator, are concurrently trained against each other. The generator (the “synthesiser” in our case) learns to produce novel data in the style of the training examples by fooling the discriminator, which tries to recognise real and fake data during training. SpecSinGAN is built upon a subset of GANs called single-image GANs (such as SinGAN [42] or ConSinGAN [43]) where, unlike other approaches that need large datasets, the data required to train the model is reduced to a single training example. In our case, the training example are the different layers of a one-shot sound effect. For instance, we use a six layer sound effect (e.g., low rumble, mid rumble, hiss, 3 crackle) split into two SpecSinGAN models (one for the three fire rumble intensities, another for the three crackles) and produce novel variations of them on demand, which will then be combined randomly to create a fire sound effect.

As in [6], we use multi-layer log-magnitude spectrograms to represent the layers of the training sound effect. These spectrograms are computed by taking the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) of the different layers using a FFT size of 512, a Hanning window of the same size and 75% overlap. From the result we discard the phase information, take a logarithm and stack the different log-magnitude spectrogram layers of the sound effect along a channel axis. We finally standardise them (0 mean, 1 standard deviation). These log-magnitude spectrograms are used to train the architecture. During inference, to transform the generated log-magnitude spectrograms into audio, we revert the standardisation, invert the logarithm and reconstruct the phase using the Griffin-Lim algorithm [44] to take the inverse short-time Fourier transform (ISTFT).

SpecSinGAN learns in a progressive growing multi-scale fashion, employing a fully convolutional GAN at each resolution and stage. At the start of the training, the model produces small spectrograms which progressively grow at each stage until the last one, where they are of the same size of the training data. The model is able to produce novel variations of the training sound effect as it uses patchGANs [45] training on overlapping patches of the spectrograms with a fixed receptive field as the training stages progress. Thanks to the fully convolutional nature of the network, once trained, SpecSinGAN is also able to produce arbitrary length spectrograms by passing a different

x -axis size noise map, potentially increasing the variability of the data. For full details of the SpecSinGAN architecture please refer to [6].

To provide the sounds used in this sonification project, we employ two SpecSinGAN models: one trained on three fire crackle sounds (each sound with a ≈ 130 ms duration) and another trained on three different intensities of a fire rumble sound (each one of them with a ≈ 500 ms duration). All the training sound effects were collected from the Freesound website [46].

To train the model producing the fire crackle sounds we employ 2000 iterations per training stage, 64 filters in the convolutional layers, a dilation rate (i.e. the spacing between the values in a kernel) of 3 in the second discriminator and a minimum tensor size of the training pyramid of 25. We use the same configuration for the fire rumble model, but using 8000 iterations per training stage and 128 filters for the convolutional layers instead. Training the models on a NVIDIA Tesla V100 took ≈ 38 min and ≈ 390 min for the fire crackle and the fire rumble model respectively. For inference, we apply a randomised $\pm 20\%$ range multiplier to the x -axis of the spectrograms of the fire crackle model (to randomise their audio length and in return increase their variation) and no randomisation to the fire rumble model (to maintain their length constant and ease the overlap operation between segments). Synthesising 50 sounds per layer (150 sounds in total) took ≈ 2.8 s and ≈ 6.2 s for the fire crackle and the fire rumble model respectively on a consumer laptop GPU (NVIDIA GTX 1050 Ti Max-Q). All the training and synthesised sounds are mono and have a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz.

3.2 Hardware

The physical hardware system is composed of a Smart Plug¹ and a RaspberryPi microcomputer. A diagram of the hardware connections can be seen in Figure 1. The Smart Plug is a device that can be inserted in an electrical socket and can measure the real-time electricity consumption of a device that is plugged into it. The Smart Plug that we have used is connected to the internet through the home WiFi network, and sends the consumption data in real-time to a proprietary database. Specifically, it measures voltage, current, temperature and active power of the socket. This data can be accessed by the users through a web service, a smartphone app or a web API. Our system uses a python script to query the API of the database to get real-time data from the plug, which is then sent to the Pure Data script through the Open Sound Control (OSC) protocol. Both the python script and the PD patch are run on a RaspberryPi 3B+, which is connected to a speaker through its mini jack output, allowing to listen to real-time sound changes corresponding to variations in electricity consumption.

3.3 Sonification

The continuous and dynamic fire sound consists of a fire base, or fire rumble, mixed with the sound of crackles. The fire base is created by mixing four randomly selected

Figure 1. Diagram of the hardware system

Figure 2. Diagram of fire base

low and middle rumbles, and hiss sounds which overlap by about 10 milliseconds. This layered sequence of four sounds lasts slightly less than 2 seconds and is continuously triggered every 1900 milliseconds creating a continuous sound. While this combination of layers and this overlap time work well to create a continuous fire sound, these characteristics may vary if other kind of sounds are used. See Figure 2

We then mix in up to 4 layers of randomly triggered crackles sounds. Each layer contains 4 crackle sounds. In the current model, we can trigger up to 16 randomly selected and randomly timed crackle sounds within 2 seconds of sound. All layers of the fire base and the crackles have separate gains to provide a realistic mix, and to be able to control the overall intensity of the fire sound and the number of crackles per second.

3.3.1 Sonification mapping

The PD patch receives electrical power data of the appliance in use via OSC. This is then mapped to a number of fire parameters with the aim to increase the intensity of the fire sound as the electrical power increases. In order to define the most appropriate sonification mapping between fire intensity - overall level of fire base, overall level of crackles and density of crackles - and electrical power, the researchers took note of the average electrical power drawn by a number of typical small household appliances such as internet speaker, laptop, TV, toaster, kettle, microwave, blender, hairdryer, etc. It became quickly apparent that many appliances draw less power than about 700W and only a few draw more (the kettle went up to 2550W, for example). We therefore decided that the sonification should vary approximately in an exponential way.

For the testing developed in this project, a low volume fire base without crackles starts when the power is 5W. Above 20W the volume of the fire base increases. At 30W the first

¹ <https://doc.smart-me.com/products/plug>

Figure 3. Diagram of crackle layers

Figure 4. Waveforms and spectrograms of the fire sound at low, middle, and high levels of electricity consumption. The horizontal axis is time in seconds.

layer of crackles is added (a density of four crackles in 2 seconds) at low volume. At 70W both the volume of the fire base and the crackles is increased. At 100W the density of crackles is doubled and so on, until at about 1500W we hear the full intensity of the fire with 16 crackles every 2 seconds with a relatively high volume for both fire base and crackles. Figure 4 shows the spectra of the fire at very low, middle and high levels of electricity consumption. We can see that the sound level of the base increases between the low and the high level of electricity consumption. The crackles are not present at low level electricity consumption. The crackles are present (as vertical lines) at middle level, and then increase in density and sound level at high levels of electricity consumption.

4. TESTING

The per-appliance energy consumption sonification was piloted tested in two households by two different researchers on a number of appliances (see Table 1).

The sonification system worked for all appliances, making particularly audible the variations in electrical power in appliances that require interaction: for example, when appliances have various operation settings (like a blender or an hair dryer), or, like computers, are interacted with often by users (opening new applications, etc.). Video examples of the sonification in use with a TV and a laptop can be seen here^{2 3}. We can see that the video shows a slight delay between an appliance drawing electricity and the resulting sound - this is due to the latency built in to the smart plug data feedback in sending the data, rather than the sound system. Overall the sonification mapping worked well in making variations audible, however this

² TV example <https://youtu.be/ZV6kts9QdZI>

³ Laptop example <https://youtu.be/hDF00Ti7bqo>

Appliances tested and energy variation	
Sonos speaker	Plugged in or playing music
Toaster	starting 2 toasts or starting 4 toasts
Kettle	ON
Blender	various settings
Smoothie maker	various settings
Filter coffee maker	making coffee vs keeping coffee warm
Coffee grinder	ON
Microwave	clock vs opening door and light inside vs cooking
Hairdryer	various settings (cold vs warm air and slow vs fast)
Laptop	typing, opening applications, etc
Internet TV	switch on, opening applications, etc

Table 1. Summary of appliances tested

could be adjusted and further improved in the future as discussed in the next section.

5. DISCUSSION

The sonification provided a very intuitive way to compare the energy consumption of different appliances. For example, the researchers were quite surprised at the difference in power drawn by a computer comparing to a kettle (a difference of about 2500W!). While this can be appreciated by looking at the numbers specified in the products or by looking at the numbers in the smart plug application, hearing the sounds made this difference starker and memorable.

The sonification also made evident the power that is drawn almost invisibly by an appliance. When a researcher connected the microwave to the sonification, they saw that simply the clock display was drawing 0.7W, but they were not expecting to hear the fire intensity increasing by opening the door of the microwave. But indeed the power increased to about 21W most likely due to the light bulb inside the microwave that is activated only when the door is open. A video example of the microwave can be seen here⁴. Whilst the light clearly has a practical purpose (particularly at night), the researcher was so unaware of it during testing that their initial reaction was to assume that the measuring system had gone awry. During the daytime, without the sonic feedback, the light became functionally invisible, and along with it the associated energy usage - which was four times higher than any other light in the apartment due to the older type of bulb used in the microwave. With the addition of real-time sonification the researcher’s attention was immediately directed to the energy usage, and they were able to more deeply understand the power draw of every aspect of the device.

The sonification also contributed to becoming aware of when electricity is *not* being used. A great deal of popu-

⁴ Microwave example https://youtu.be/LOk_jR_fBvEQ

lar media focuses on so-called "vampire devices" that draw electricity even when on standby [47], this real-time sonification allows an effective method to show that in many cases this is not necessarily true. While testing the TV and sound system, for example, the sonification system made immediately clear that the audio amplifier was indeed drawing electricity when switched on and not in use (about 11W), however the "standby" mode (which activates automatically after some time) removed this completely, dropping down to almost 0. Similarly, the laptop charger drew no electricity at all when plugged into the wall, however as soon as it was connected to the computer the sonification gave the feedback indicating the steady 60W used to charge the battery.

In this regard, this sonification of energy consumption can promote an increase awareness of what is happening in the household, contributing to unveiling the complexities [48] of the energy systems that surround us and that have consequences both at an individual level (in terms of energy bills, for example) and at a more general level (in terms of unnecessary energy consumption, for example).

The current prototype uses the built-in audio system of the Raspberry Pi to output the sound. This provided considerable benefits in the first stage of development in terms of rapid prototyping and bug-fixing, as we could connect the system to any speaker or set of headphones to hear the resulting sonification. It also raised questions regarding how the sound could be generated and integrated more tightly into a single object, resulting in a more seamless and potentially intuitive interface for sonic feedback. We thus aim to further develop this prototype, making it into a stand alone object with a small speaker that can be inserted between the socket and the appliance and immediately produce the sonification as power is drawn. This moves the prototype towards the metaphor of an "energy stethoscope" that would allow all members of the family to become aware of the power consumption in an intuitive manner.

In regard to the system, in this project we use SpecSinGAN offline, producing the sounds on a different hardware and storing them as audio files for the sonification. While we arguably synthesised enough sounds (50 sounds per layer per model, 300 in total) to provide a dynamic soundscape that never repeats itself, for future work we plan to explore the idea of using a model directly on target hardware. This will allow to produce new batches of sounds on demand, potentially increasing the variability. These new synthesised sounds could also be classified or conditioned on high-level descriptors (e.g., brightness, roughness), allowing a finer control over the sonification.

We speculate that a future and more general implementation of this system could allow users to personalise the sonification by choosing a different source sound or even by starting from a sound that they have recorded. This would allow researchers to experiment with different metaphors between sounds and energy concepts, as well as investigate how using personal sound might affect our perception of energy consumption.

The study thus far has also focused on a single plug at a

time, but the granular nature of smart plug measurements offer the potential to consider the design of a sonification system that takes into account multiple streams of electricity consumption data coming from a smart meter - further work could look into how different sonic feedback systems running concurrently could interact or layer with each other in an effective manner.

6. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a novel method to sonify the energy consumption of household appliances. This method is based on creating a sonification based on an everyday sound - the sound of fire - which makes the display highly intuitive. We synthesise a continuous fire effect by utilising SpecSinGAN, an unconditional generative architecture that takes a single one-shot sound effect and produces novel variations of it. The advantage of using this technique is that we can create highly dynamic and "organic" sonifications based on everyday sounds, or even personally recorded sounds, that might be more easily accepted and engaged with by users on a day to day basis in their homes. We report on how we pilot tested the system in two households, as well as discuss results and future work.

Acknowledgments

This work is carried out in the context of the Sound for Energy research project ⁵ funded by Swedish Energy Agency (Project No. 51645-1). This work was also supported by the EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Intelligent Games & Game Intelligence (IGGI) [EP/L015846/1] and Sony Interactive Entertainment Europe.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] T. Hargreaves, M. Nye, and J. Burgess, "Keeping energy visible? exploring how householders interact with feedback from smart energy monitors in the longer term," *Energy policy*, vol. 52, pp. 126–134, 2013.
- [2] T. Hargreaves, "Beyond energy feedback," *Building Research & Information*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 332–342, 2018.
- [3] W. Gaver, "Designing for homo ludens," *I3 Magazine*, vol. 12, no. June, pp. 2–6, 2002.
- [4] P. Vannini and J. Taggart, *Off the grid: re-assembling domestic life*. Routledge, 2014.
- [5] A. R. Menon, B. Hedin, and E. Eriksson, "Expanding affective computing paradigms through animistic design principles," in *Human-Computer Interaction—INTERACT 2021: 18th IFIP TC 13 International Conference, Bari, Italy, August 30–September 3, 2021, Proceedings, Part I 18*. Springer, 2021, pp. 115–135.
- [6] A. Barahona-Ríos and T. Collins, "SpecSinGAN: Sound Effect Variation Synthesis Using Single-Image

⁵ <https://soundforenergy.net>

- GANs,” in *19th Sound and Music Computing Conference, Saint-Étienne, France, 2022*.
- [7] S. Pauletto, “Film and theatre-based approaches for sonic interaction design,” *Digital Creativity*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 15–26, 2014.
- [8] A. Mahdavi, C. Berger, H. Amin, E. Ampatzi, R. K. Andersen, E. Azar, V. M. Barthelmes, M. Favero, J. Hahn, D. Khovalyg *et al.*, “The role of occupants in buildings’ energy performance gap: myth or reality?” *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 6, p. 3146, 2021.
- [9] M. Schweiker, “Understanding occupants’ behaviour for energy efficiency in buildings,” *Current Sustainable/Renewable Energy Reports*, vol. 4, pp. 8–14, 2017.
- [10] L. Pereira, F. Quintal, M. Barreto, and N. J. Nunes, “Understanding the limitations of eco-feedback: a one-year long-term study,” in *Human-Computer Interaction and Knowledge Discovery in Complex, Unstructured, Big Data: Third International Workshop, HCI-KDD 2013, Held at SouthCHI 2013, Maribor, Slovenia, July 1-3, 2013. Proceedings*. Springer, 2013, pp. 237–255.
- [11] O. Alharbi and S. Chatterjee, “Greencrowd: An iot-based smartphone app for residential electricity conservation,” in *Designing the Digital Transformation: 12th International Conference, DESRIST 2017, Karlsruhe, Germany, May 30–June 1, 2017, Proceedings 12*. Springer, 2017, pp. 348–363.
- [12] A. Gustafsson, M. Bång, and M. Svahn, “Power explorer: a casual game style for encouraging long term behavior change among teenagers,” in *Proceedings of the international conference on advances in computer entertainment technology*, 2009, pp. 182–189.
- [13] S. Darby *et al.*, “The effectiveness of feedback on energy consumption,” *A Review for DEFRA of the Literature on Metering, Billing and direct Displays*, vol. 486, no. 2006, p. 26, 2006.
- [14] Z. Zhongming, L. Linong, Y. Xiaona, Z. Wangqiang, L. Wei *et al.*, “Achieving energy efficiency through behaviour change: what does it take?” 2013.
- [15] K. Buchanan, R. Russo, and B. Anderson, “Feeding back about eco-feedback: How do consumers use and respond to energy monitors?” *Energy Policy*, vol. 73, pp. 138–146, 2014.
- [16] S. Utopia and Y. Strengers, “Smart energy technologies in everyday life.”
- [17] M. Sohn, T. Nam, and W. Lee, “Designing with unconscious human behaviors for eco-friendly interaction,” in *CHI’09 Extended Abstracts on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 2009, pp. 2651–2654.
- [18] M. Bang, A. Gustafsson, and C. Katzeff, “Promoting new patterns in household energy consumption with pervasive learning games,” in *Persuasive Technology: Second International Conference on Persuasive Technology, PERSUASIVE 2007, Palo Alto, CA, USA, April 26-27, 2007, Revised Selected Papers 2*. Springer, 2007, pp. 55–63.
- [19] A. Gustafsson and M. Gyllenswård, “The power-aware cord: energy awareness through ambient information display,” in *CHI’05 extended abstracts on Human factors in computing systems*, 2005, pp. 1423–1426.
- [20] L. Broms, C. Katzeff, M. Bång, Å. Nyblom, S. I. Hjelm, and K. Ehrnberger, “Coffee maker patterns and the design of energy feedback artefacts,” in *proceedings of the 8th ACM conference on designing interactive systems*, 2010, pp. 93–102.
- [21] J. Pierce and E. Paulos, “Materializing energy,” in *Proceedings of the 8th ACM Conference on Designing Interactive Systems*, 2010, pp. 113–122.
- [22] L. Fickert, G. Eckel, W. Nagler, A. De Campo, and E. Schmutzner, “New development of teaching concepts in multimedia learning for electrical power systems introducing sonification,” *Paper, Region*, vol. 8, 2006.
- [23] P. Cowden and L. Dosiak, “Auditory displays of electric power grids.” Georgia Institute of Technology, 2018.
- [24] J. Hammerschmidt, R. Tunnermann, and T. Hermann, “Infodrops: Sonification for enhanced awareness of resource consumption in the shower.” Georgia Institute of Technology, 2013.
- [25] K. Groß-Vogt, M. Weger, R. Höldrich, T. Hermann, T. Bovermann, and S. Reichmann, “Augmentation of an institute’s kitchen: An ambient auditory display of electric power consumption.” Georgia Institute of Technology, 2018.
- [26] S. Pauletto, “The voice delivers the threats, foley delivers the punch: Embodied knowledge in foley artistry,” in *The Routledge Companion to Screen Music and Sound*. Routledge, 2017, pp. 338–348.
- [27] Y. Seznec and S. Pauletto, “Towards a workshop methodology for involving non-expert stakeholders in the interactive sound design process: Connecting household sounds and energy consumption data.” Georgia Institute of Technology, 2022.
- [28] ———, “The singing shower: A melody-sensitive interface for physical interaction and efficient energy consumption,” in *Sound and Music Computing Conference, June 2022, 2022*.
- [29] V. Madaghiele and S. Pauletto, “Experimenting techniques for sonic implicit interactions: a real time sonification of body-textile heat exchange with sound augmented fabrics,” in *Conference on the Sonification of Health and Environmental Data*, 2022.

- [30] J. Engel, C. Resnick, A. Roberts, S. Dieleman, M. Norouzi, D. Eck, and K. Simonyan, “Neural Audio Synthesis of Musical Notes With Wavenet Autoencoders,” in *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning-Volume 70*. JMLR.org, 2017, pp. 1068–1077.
- [31] A. Barahona-Ríos and S. Pauletto, “Synthesising Knocking Sound Effects Using Conditional WaveGAN,” in *17th Sound and Music Computing Conference, Online*, 2020.
- [32] X. Liu, T. Iqbal, J. Zhao, Q. Huang, M. D. Plumbley, and W. Wang, “Conditional Sound Generation Using Neural Discrete Time-Frequency Representation Learning,” in *2021 IEEE 31st International Workshop on Machine Learning for Signal Processing (MLSP)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [33] M. Comunità, H. Phan, and J. D. Reiss, “Neural Synthesis of Footsteps Sound Effects with Generative Adversarial Networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.09605*, 2021.
- [34] S. Andreu and M. V. Aylagas, “Neural Synthesis of Sound Effects Using Flow-Based Deep Generative Models,” in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Interactive Digital Entertainment*, vol. 18, no. 1, 2022, pp. 2–9.
- [35] F. Kreuk, G. Synnaeve, A. Polyak, U. Singer, A. Défossez, J. Copet, D. Parikh, Y. Taigman, and Y. Adi, “AudioGen: Textually Guided Audio Generation,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2209.15352*, 2022.
- [36] H. Liu, Z. Chen, Y. Yuan, X. Mei, X. Liu, D. Mandic, W. Wang, and M. D. Plumbley, “AudioLDM: Text-to-Audio Generation with Latent Diffusion Models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.12503*, 2023.
- [37] R. Huang, J. Huang, D. Yang, Y. Ren, L. Liu, M. Li, Z. Ye, J. Liu, X. Yin, and Z. Zhao, “Make-An-Audio: Text-To-Audio Generation with Prompt-Enhanced Diffusion Models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.12661*, 2023.
- [38] G. Greshler, T. R. Shaham, and T. Michaeli, “Catch-A-Waveform: Learning to Generate Audio from a Single Short Example,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2106.06426*, 2021.
- [39] D. B. Lloyd, N. Raghuvanshi, and N. K. Govindaraju, “Sound Synthesis for Impact Sounds in Video Games,” in *Symposium on Interactive 3D Graphics and Games*, 2011, pp. 55–62.
- [40] J. Fagerström, S. J. Schlecht, V. Välimäki *et al.*, “One-to-Many Conversion for Percussive Samples,” in *International Conference on Digital Audio Effects*, 2021, pp. 129–135.
- [41] I. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio, “Generative adversarial nets,” *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 27, 2014.
- [42] T. R. Shaham, T. Dekel, and T. Michaeli, “SinGAN: Learning a Generative Model From a Single Natural Image,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, 2019, pp. 4570–4580.
- [43] T. Hinz, M. Fisher, O. Wang, and S. Wermter, “Improved Techniques for Training Single-Image GANs,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conference on Applications of Computer Vision*, 2021, pp. 1300–1309.
- [44] D. Griffin and J. Lim, “Signal Estimation From Modified Short-Time Fourier Transform,” *IEEE Transactions on acoustics, speech, and signal processing*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 236–243, 1984.
- [45] P. Isola, J.-Y. Zhu, T. Zhou, and A. A. Efros, “Image-To-Image Translation With Conditional Adversarial Networks,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2017, pp. 1125–1134.
- [46] F. Font, G. Roma, and X. Serra, “Freesound Technical Demo,” in *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Multimedia*, 2013, pp. 411–412.
- [47] M. Cieslak and T. Gerken, “Energy supplier counts cost of devices on standby,” *BBC News*, Apr. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-61235367>
- [48] T. Hargreaves, C. Wilson, and R. Hauxwell-Baldwin, “Learning to live in a smart home,” *Building Research & Information*, vol. 46, no. 1, pp. 127–139, 2018.